

Name of Publisher: BRIGHT EDUCATION RESEARCH SOLUTIONS

Area of Publication: Business, Management and Accounting (miscellaneous)

Journal of Management & Social Science

ISSN Online: 3006-4848
ISSN Print: 3006-483X

<https://rjmss.com/index.php/1/about>

RECOGNIZED IN "Y"
CATEGORY BY

The Impact of Learning & Development and Communication Skills on Employee Performance in the Information Technology Sector of Pakistan: A Mediated Moderated Study

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Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of Learning & Development (L&D) and Communication Skills on Employee Performance in Pakistan's IT sector, examining Career Adaptability as a mediating factor and Intrinsic Motivation as a moderator. Despite investments in employee development, organizations face challenges in sustaining performance due to rapid technological changes and dynamic work demands. A quantitative survey was conducted among 72 software industry employees, utilizing validated scales for L&D, Communication Skills, Career Adaptability, Intrinsic Motivation, and Employee Performance. Reliability and validity of constructs were confirmed using Cronbach's alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Regression and bootstrapped moderated mediation analyses (Hayes, 2022, PROCESS Model 14) revealed that L&D significantly predicts Employee Performance directly and indirectly via Career Adaptability, while Communication Skills influence performance fully through Career Adaptability. Intrinsic Motivation strengthened the effect of Career Adaptability on performance, highlighting the role of internal drive in leveraging adaptive resources. The findings support the integration of Career Construction Theory, and Self-Determination Theory, emphasizing the importance of adaptability-focused development and motivational strategies. Practical implications for HR and L&D managers include designing training programs to foster adaptability and structuring roles to enhance intrinsic motivation. Limitations and directions for future research are discussed.

Keywords: Employee Performance, Learning & Development, Communication Skills, Career Adaptability, Intrinsic Motivation, IT Sector, Mediation, Moderation.

Introduction

Modern business realities, typified by the high growth rates and stiff competition, continue to depend more on the workforce strengths that are based on strategic alignment. Technological competence should not be regarded as the only factor that affects employee performance because a large skills base, versatility, and intrinsic motivation should also be included. Starting with Learning and Development (L&D) interventions and communication competencies are essential antecedents of performance, and help to obtain, share, and successfully implement knowledge at the organisational level (Arulsamy, Singh, and Panchal, 2023; Wang, 2024). Workforce adaptability mediates the relationship between learning, communication and performance since it moderates the role of L&D and communication on performance outcomes Wulandari, F., et al. (2020). This has led to adaptability being regarded as especially timely at times of turbulence (Illinois Gies Business, 2023). The characteristics of organisational operations such as high rate of technological innovation, fluctuation in financial figures, and changes in the global marketplace (Gagne et al., 2022) require employees that are not only able to cope with the existing duties but also adapt to the ongoing change, acquire new skills, and participate in career growth (Chouhan, 2023). This has led to a change of employee performance evaluation, which has been based on the ability to complete tasks to a more adaptive ability and enduring involvement. In the

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past, employee performance has been seen as the keystone of organisational performance. But modern research instead thinks of it as a complex construct that is being driven by the background competencies, psychological resources, and motivation (Hosen et al., 2023). In this context, Learning and Development (L&D) and communication competencies are formal and informal platforms that enable organisations to offer knowledge to employees, build teamwork, promote feedback, and align with organisational objectives (Balakrishnan et al., 2024; Flegl, 2022). However, organisational investments in L&D and communication do not always have positive results. The empirical information shows that the amount of training is not as decisive as the quality of training and mechanisms of its implementation (Flegl, 2022). Besides, the success of communication is dependent on personal competency and emotional intelligence (Melvina, 2024). In its turn, it is essential to explain the psychological processes and situational variables that maximize the use of L&D and communication. In the current research, a moderated mediation model is utilized where L&D and communication competencies are assumed to have an effect on employee performance through the career adaptability mediating between them, where intrinsic motivation serves as the moderator of indirect relationship.

Problem Statement

Information Technology (IT) industry is a branch of Pakistan economy and export, which is encountering significant responsibilities in maintaining the level of employee performance in the face of dynamic rapid technological development and increased competition in the global market. Information technology (IT) industry consisting The information technology (IT)-enabled services, software development, freelancing, and other digital industry sector are critical to the economy of Pakistan. It is a high-growth, export vehicle, which contributes to foreign exchange earnings, employment generation (especially among the youth and the women), diversifying of the economic structure and enabling technological leapfrogging with the structural issue in the conventional sector like agriculture and textile. Scholarly literature focuses on the importance of the sector in increasing productivity, innovation, and GDP growth by ICT investment and diffusion. Empirical data, such as, (Rehman et al. 2021), indicate that ICT investment and diffusion has a positive and significant long-term effect on expanding the Pakistan economy, thus acting as facilitator of efficiency increment in various industries.

Despite the fact that organizations seek to dedicate huge resources to learning and development (L&D) programs and communication skills development, such programs are often not sufficient to facilitate homogenous and sustainable performance improvements.

Pakistani IT experts face skills obsolescence that can be related to the rapid changes in technology and the dynamic nature of the work requirements. This means that workers usually have problems with applying obtained knowledge and language skills into constructive performances in the conditions of uncertainty. To mitigate the shortcomings in performance, it is important to take into consideration the adaptive abilities and motivational mood of employees on a holistic basis and this can lead to the correct utilization of skills. Lack of productivity of workforce poses serious challenges to

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organizational sustainability within the digital economy of the world.

Research Gap

Although an increasing body of literature in the context of Pakistan studies the issue of learning and development (L&D) as a predictor of organizational performance, employee commitment, and career advancement (Ahmed et al., 2025; Zafar, 2024), few of them simultaneously research the independent impact of L&D practices and communication competencies on employee performance. In addition, little attention has been given to mediating role of psychosocial resources (e.g. career adaptability) or moderating effect of intrinsic motivation in these associations.

The available literature confirms positive links between L&D initiatives, communication competencies, and performance outcomes (Hosen et al., 2024; Balakrishnan et al., 2024), but it does not pay much attention to multistage processes of the transformation of these antecedents into long-term, durable performance. Namely, there are few studies by Pakistani authors that examine the role of career adaptability (concern, control, curiosity, and confidence) in the mediation between organizational resources (L&D and communication) and adaptive performance to volatile working conditions. Career adaptability is based on the Career Construction Theory (CCT), showing that the successful operation in modern and dynamic work areas depends on the necessary psychosocial resources (Chen et al., 2024; Mirza and Chaudhary, 2025).

In addition, the effectiveness of L&D and communication inputs depends on the intrinsic motivation of the employees which, according to Self-Determination Theory (SDT), is associated with autonomy, competence, and relatedness as the forces that lead to internalized skills application and proactive behaviour (Ryan and Deci, 2022; McAnally et al., 2024). More intrinsically motivated employees will be more willing to learn and engage in the communication process via an active, active and dynamic application of the newly gained knowledge and communication skills (Nazim et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2024). These gaps are filled by the current study testing empirically a moderated mediation model, whereby L&D and communication skills represent the independent predictors of employee performance, and career adaptability mediates the connections between L/communication skills and career adaptability to performance, and intrinsic motivation mediates these connections. It is an integrated framework since it offers a more detailed explanation of how organizational interventions can lead to adaptive, high-performance results in the Pakistani context.

Literature Review

Conceptualization of Variables

Employee Performance

Employee performance refers to those behavioral attributes that can be witnessed to have a substantive contribution on the organizational goals (Hosen et al., 2023; Mirza and Chaudhary, 2025). In modern research, the performance is divided into performance task and performance contextual or adaptive (Wu et al., 2025). Task performance considers job specific tasks, Consistency, and Innovation, lifelong learning, and professional growth (Chouhan, 2023). In this study, adaptive performance is a holistic measure which is of priority.

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Learning & Development

Learning and development (L&D) refers to the premeditated and structured process within an organization aimed at imparting knowledge, skills, and competencies to its employees to enable them to be better prepared to handle the present and future roles (Pengestika et al., 2023). This has a wide range of interventions, between formal classroom training and specialized workshops (formal L&D) and coaching, mentorship, job rotation, and informal self-directed e-learning (informal L&D). There is evidence to consistently support the hypothesis that L&D programs are positively related to predicting work performance, which can be explained by facilitating a range of mechanisms, including improved competence and organisational commitment (Hosen et al., 2023; Pengestika et al., 2023).

However, a vital aspect of L&D effectiveness, which is often discussed in the literature on transfer-training research (Flegl, 2022; Mehner, 2025), is a transfer climate and motivation to transfer in an individual. The provision of training is not enough but its effectiveness requires organizational support and psychological readiness of the employee to use training to the requirements of the job. In this respect, L&D is presented in this study as the perception of an employee with regard to the quality and access to systematic possibilities to develop job-related abilities and knowledge, which directly determines his/her revelation of competence, which is a fundamental psychological requirement described in Self-Determination Theory.

Communication Skills

Workplace communication skills include the ability of an individual to transmit, receive, and interpret information of various modalities successfully and thus fosters collaboration, reduces conflict, and maintains the clarity of organizational goals (Balakrishnan et al., 2024; Melvina, 2024). This variable is an independent variable to learning and development (L&D) since it focuses on the use of interpersonal and structural interaction competence as opposed to the formal learning of technical knowledge. Communication includes the vertical communication flows between the manager and subordinate in terms of manager-to-subordinate feedback and directives, as well as peer-to-peer communication and sharing knowledge among peers. Empirical research demonstrates that efficient communication seems to be associated with excellent work performance and is generally connected with other vital workplace skills, including emotional intelligence controlling the transfer and delivery of sensitive information (Melvina, 2024). One of the key antecedents is communication, as the process of adaptation and implementation of learned skills (adaptability) is inherently relational, and it involves constant negotiation, solicitation of feedback, and alignment with other people (Balakrishnan et al., 2024). The relatedness psychological need is directly supported by communication of high quality; thus, making the employees feel connected, understood, and integrated into a cooperative environment all the factors that are vital in psychological safety and incorporation of risk-taking behavior required in adaptation.

Career Adaptability

Another important psychosocial resource is career adaptability, which displays the

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willingness and ability of the individual to respond to the existing and future career development challenges, career transitions, and job-related traumas (Chen, Wang, & Li, 2024; Chen, Li, and Gao, 2024). Being one of the fundamental principles of the Career Construction Theory (CCT), it refers to a self-regulatory ability that is dynamic, facilitating how people deal with their careers. It is not a fixed characteristic but a set of psychological resources which can be developed with the help of experience or with the help of an organization and therefore serves as an effective mediator. The construct itself contains four separate dimensions or what is colloquially known as (the) 4Cs: Concern, Control, Curiosity, and Confidence (Hassan et al., 2024).

Concern: This dimension is associated with how much a person makes plans and prepares in the future of their career path. It entails the orientation towards future and thinking in terms of what one would do now to achieve the preferred future. The state of psychological readiness to future professional activities is called concern (Chouhan, 2023).

Control: This dimension is associated with a sense of ownership and responsibility of a given career path to an individual. It entails agency action, choice action, and having the perceived agency to do what they value in their now and the future in their occupation, which is highly congruent with autonomy need as described in Self-Determination Theory (SDT).

Curiosity: This dimension reflects on the active research of possible career opportunities, jobs, and personal understanding. It indicates a desire to explore its suitability to the different work settings and the desire to learn something new, therefore, remaining relevant in a changing workplace environment (Chen, Wang and Li, 2024).

Confidence: This dimension is the self-efficacy conviction that a person can effectively perform the adaptive actions, resolve the profession-related issues, and overcome the challenges. It demonstrates the belief in own abilities to succeed in the situation and work well under new circumstances (Liu et al., 2025).

Career adaptability is strongly supported by empirical studies as a precursor to such desirable results as work engagement (Chen, Wang, and Li, 2024) and future performance (Chouhan, 2023). Notably, the Confidence (via the teaching of skills) and Control (via the explanation of career paths) can be directly promoted by the L&D programs, whereas the communication skills can be used to promote Curiosity and Concern (by helping to acquire information and feedback). Thereupon, career adaptability acts as the key to connecting organizational support and performance results (Chen, Li, and Gao, 2024).

Intrinsic Motivation (Moderating Variable)

The concept of intrinsic motivation can be defined in conjunction with the Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Deci, 2022) as the desire and the act of performing a particular activity without any distinct outcomes, such as the reward, the punishment, or any external pressure. This motivation is the highest point of the SDT scale which is self-determination and deep involvement. In comparison, extrinsic motivation implies an activity that is done to achieve a solitary result, such as salary raise or promotion. Psychological well-being, advanced levels of learning, ability to endure even when things are going wrong, and creativity have high correlations with intrinsic motivation (McAnally

et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024). It is in a performance context where the quality of effort thrown into it is determined. An intrinsically motivated worker, in turn, does not simply participate in a learning and development (L&D) session to pass the check; on the contrary, the given person actively incorporates the newly obtained knowledge, challenges themselves with hard-to-do assignments, and constantly utilize those skills in unusual, adaptive problems (Nazim et al., 2022). Seeing that the development and the application of adaptability require significant effort, self-regulation, and patience (Chouhan, 2023), intrinsic motivation is theorized to be a strong boundary condition, which strengthens the motivational relationship between organizational inputs and readiness of the employee to take part in the challenging process of striving and developing adaptive behaviours. Therefore, it is the inner nourishment to turn the possibility of L&D and communication into the established resource of adaptability.

Theoretical Foundation

The measures used in the study are mainly based on the two classic theories which when combined bring a strong framework in explaining the relations that should be expected:

- Self-Determination Theory (SDT)
- Career Construction Theory (CCT).

Self-Determination Theory (SDT)

As defined by Ryan and Deci (2022) as well as situated by (Gagne et al. 2022) and (McAnally et al. 2024) into the specifics of the contemporary workplaces, SDT offers the prism through which the significant mediating power of motivation can be considered. The SDT states that human beings have three universal, intrinsic, Basic Psychological Needs (BPNs) including autonomy, relatedness, and competence.

Autonomy: Autonomy can be described as the feeling of power, will and determination over the actions of the individual and that, no behavior is imposed upon the individual.

Competence: Competence, is the feeling of competence, prowess, and efficacy in his or her surrounding and undertakings.

Relatedness: Relatedness refers to a sense of belonging, affiliation to others and being taken care of by people or social entities of importance.

As soon as the workplace is carefully conceived to please these BPNs, subjects internalize values and rules, thus, developing high-quality intrinsic motivation. On the other hand, conditions that undermine such needs lead to extrinsic motivation or demotivation (Ryan and Deci, 2022).

The conceptualization of L&D programmes in the suggested model might be seen as the organisational resources that meet the Competence requirement in imparting the knowledge and skills necessary to master it. The need of Relatedness is mostly achieved through high-quality communication skills and positive feedback climate that permits employees to feel valued and socially related. The Autonomy experience is required in itself even in the manifestation of intrinsic motivation.

The theoretical suggestion to the already existing model is that L&D and communication skills do not act as direct performance drivers, but they serve as precursors to BPNs satisfaction. In the case in which such organisational inputs are highly rated i.e. fulfilling the BPNs, the result is the stimulation of strong intrinsic motivation.

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This motive instinct then acts as an influential magnifier or regulator, determining how an employee takes the input in their ambitions to become adaptable in the profession. As such, the intrinsic motivation is estimated to improve the efficiency of these organisational resources, in accordance with the SDT principle that the levels of self-determination define the quality and sustainability of utilising the resource (McAnally et al., 2024). A motivating employee will not simply sit in a training session, the person will have a desire to find a way of applying the newly learnt skills in daily operations by utilizing an augmented sense of control (Autonomy) and competence to develop an adaptable quality.

Career Construction Theory (CCT)

The theory of construct of career adaptability, which is supported by Career Construct Theory (CCT), suggests that career has to be constructed with the use of making meaningful, self-directed and adaptive responses to tasks of vocation as well as societal demands (Chen et al., 2024). The theory also goes beyond the traditional models of traits factors, in that it views career as a subjective dynamic process that is influenced by contextual factors and individual agency.

The CCT model is usually defined as a linear process that includes four phases (Wu et al., 2025):

Adaptive Readiness (Personality Traits): The mental characteristics (e.g., the proactive personality) which predetermine a person to handle career problems.

Adaptive Resources (Career Adaptability): 4 Cs (Concern, Control, Curiosity, Confidence) that are psychosocial resources that are acquired over a lifetime.

Adaptive Responses (Behaviors): The actual adaptive behaviors, which may be work engagement, job search behaviors or training seeking behaviors.

Adaptive Results (Outcomes): The ensuing outcomes, such as performance, job satisfaction, and wellbeing.

This paper makes CCT operational as it places Learning and Development (L&D) and Communication Skills as central organizational contributions that proactively contribute to Adaptive Resources (Career Adaptability). L&D can provide the material and format required to foster Confidence and Control, and high-quality Communication can provide the relational and informational background that arouses Curiosity and Concern. Focusing on the Career Adaptability as the central force, the model has proven to bridge the gap connecting the organizational environment and individual performance outcomes, which provide a deeper explanatory model as compared to the direct models. This resulting better Employee Performance is therefore considered the final Adaptation Result therefore qualifying the framework of CCT in the modern context of organizations (Chouhan, 2023).

The Self-determination Theory (SDT) recognizes a moderator of the motivational quality mechanism- intrinsic motivation that determines the efficiency of fulfillment of the basic needs (BPNs) as well as development of adaptability of the learning and development (L&D) initiative and communications practices. Adaptation process the component of cognitive constructivist Theory (CCT) provides a channel through which motivated resources are channeled into performance in volatile situations, which is the

case in the IT sector in Pakistan. These theoretical frameworks, working together explain the reason why the work of L&D and communication may not always be a direct driver of performance: over these theories depends the ability to generate sustained performance results including agility, innovation and retention, which are key performance determinants of the IT sector in Pakistan, faced with the modern competitive, dynamic global context.

Development of Hypotheses and Statement of Hypothesis

Direct Relationships and L&D to Performance

The primary purpose of Learning and Development (L&D) is to improve the skills gap and add to employee knowledge and thus make the fulfillment of key job roles more efficient, which, in turn, would increase the performance of tasks (Hosen et al., 2023; Flegl, 2022). Moreover, the coordination, reduction of ambiguity and error, and strengthening of requisite interpersonal relationships which are directly related to the evaluation of team and individual's performance are made through good communication (Balakrishnan et al., 2024; Melvina, 2024).

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Learning & Development positively affects Employee Performance

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Communication Skills positively affect Employee Performance

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Learning & Development positively affects Career Adaptability

Hypothesis 4 (H 4): Communication Skills positively affect Career Adaptability

The Mediating Role of Career Adaptability

Career adaptability is a dynamic psychological asset that may be enhanced by the assistance of the organization (Chen, Wang, and Li, 2024). This research is based on the assumption that the development of this resource is fronted by the environmental antecedents of L&D and Communication. L&D is a direct provider of the technical knowledge and behavioral models that the adaptive behavior needs, hence boosting the employee confidence (belief about the skill) and control perceptions (understanding the system). In this regard, effective communication helps employees to seek the feedback needed, compromise roles, and consider various career opportunities (curiosity and concern), thus, taking charge of their career transitions (Balakrishnan et al., 2024). This excellent resource of adaptability, when it is strengthened, is successfully used by the employee to release adaptive responses, which further result in high contextual and task performance (Chouhan, 2023). Adaptability is therefore put in place as the cognitive-behavioral interface that is required to join organizational investment and resultant performance outcomes.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): Career Adaptability directly affects Employee Performance

The Moderating Role of Intrinsic Motivation

Self-Determination theory described intrinsic motivation is the best form of psychological drive (Ryan and Deci, 2022). Creating career adaptability as shifting between a newly mastered skill to a proactive adaptive behavior is not an easy task and requires a long-term process of cognitive focus and energy (Nazim et al., 2022). Being intrinsically motivated, employees become more engaged, more willing to learn the learning inputs provided by L&D and the communication process, as well as ready to dedicate the appropriate amount of psychological resources to absorb new skills and utilize them

preemptively in regret in developing their resources of adaptability (McAnally et al., 2024). Without intrinsic motivation, the organizational resources can be seen as nothing more than a mandatory status or as an outside force which limits thorough processing and implementation of flexible growth based on it. According to this study, the first stage of mediation process that is the relationship between the organizational inputs and resource development (adaptability) was reinforced through intrinsic motivation which gives the necessary internal impulse.

Hypothesis 6 (H6): Intrinsic Motivation moderates the relationship between Career Adaptability and Employee Performance

Integrated Mediation Moderation

This study incorporates the mediating role of adaptability plus the moderating role of intrinsic motivation, thus the study proposes a comprehensive and conditional model. The findings of the work by (Purba et al. 2019) are quite explicit in showing that career adaptability mediates fully between career management, which contains organizational development programs and training courses, and the career success defined as an increase in performance and similar outcomes. The model assumes that indirect benefits of organizational inputs are not universal, but depend on the inner state of an employee. This integration provides the most detailed explanation to the variability of performance when it comes to different segments of employees.

Hypothesis 7 (H7): Career Adaptability mediates the relationship between Learning & Development and Employee Performance

Hypothesis 8 (H8): Career Adaptability mediates the relationship between Communication Skills and Employee Performance

Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

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Methodology

The key components of the discussed research methodology provide a thorough comprehension of the research philosophy, the employed research methodology, the research design, sampling technique data collection specifics, the data analysis technique, and instrumentation. The following chapter describes the current study methodology used to determine the relationship between Learning and Development, Communication Skills and Employee Performance, mediating the role of Career Adaptability and Intrinsic Motivation as a moderator. This chapter explains the logic behind the chosen research design, the methods of data-collection, be they the tools of analysis, therefore defines a systematic approach in manner in which these variables were quantified, observed, and analyzed.

Purpose of the Study

The core goal of the research is to prove the presumed hypothesis. It involves direct, mediating, and moderating the relationships between the variables. The hypotheses are formulated to answer the research questions and to test how the identified variables relate and assume impacts on each other, by means of the empirical testing of hypotheses. This research seeks to provide substantive contributions to the available literature.

Research Design

The research methodology approach has been taken in understanding the cause and effect relationships between the independent variables (Learning and Development, Communication Skills), the dependent variable (Employee Performance), the moderator (Intrinsic Motivation), and the mediator (Career Adaptability).

Research Philosophy

The philosophical approach that directs the gathering, analysis and analysis of data is based on positivism that argues that knowledge should be based on observable and measurable phenomena. This view focuses on objectivity, empirical data and scientific procedure, specifically strict testing of the hypotheses.

Research Methodology

The empirical validation of the study was done using quantitative, survey-based research. The hypotheses which were advanced were tested and the model proved to be valid. The quantitative methodology was a questionnaire that measured the Learning and Development, Communication Skills, Career Adaptability and Intrinsic Motivation. This methodology anticipates experimentation, gauges, and suppositions and grounds. Figure 1 represents the hypothesized model.

Research Approach

The use of deductive approach was occasioned by the fact that it tests a particular hypothesis based upon existing theories. This is initiated by a general hypothesis followed by an evaluation on the implications of the latter, it can either be corroborated or refuted. The results therefore are used to confirm or verify existing theories.

Time Horizon

The paper relies on a cross-sectional interpretation of research on the data collected at a point of time among participants in comparison to longitudinal study.

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Unit of Analysis

Seventy-two employees were the study's analysis units for the current study. A questionnaire was delivered online to the chosen companies' email addresses.

Type of Study

An explanatory correlation study is structured to conduct this research, focusing on collecting data to explain the variables of interest, figure out how they relate, and describe the relationship patterns. This study explores the relationships between two variables without establishing causation.

Population

The data was collected from the software industry of Pakistan registered with the Pakistan Software Export Board (PSEB). According to PSEB, there are a total of 2500 registered software firms. The questionnaires were distributed to software industry employees.

Sample Size

A sample questionnaire was distributed, and data was collected from the software industry employees. The research focused on registered software offices in Islamabad and Rawalpindi.

Sampling Technique

A convenience sampling technique was used for this research; it is a non-probability sampling technique in which there is no pattern in acquiring the responses. In this sampling technique, researchers can collect data from a convenient available pool of respondents.

Data Analysis

All information acquired through questionnaires was processed using the statistical program SPSS for social sciences. First, the data is checked for missing values. Then, whether each measurement model construct is valid and reliable is decided. (Field, 2005) states that when the composite dependability of each variable is more significant than 0.8, outstanding scale reliability is verified. Convergent and discriminant validity analysis is used to determine the validity of each variable. Convergent validity is established if the constructs have an average variance extracted (AVE) value of 0.5 or greater.

Data Ethics

Ethical considerations were a priority in this research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and steps were taken to keep their anonymity and confidentiality. The study was conducted complying with ethical guidelines.

Instrumentation

In its nature the survey is represented by a Likert scale consisting of a number of points, taken from already published papers, which illustrate the level of agreement or disagreement. This scale is instrumental in the measurement of the perception of respondents since it measures it on different dimensions. In particular, the rating between one and five will mean very strong disagreement and very strong agreement respectively.

Learning and Development

In the case of the Learning and Development construct, an eight-item scale that was

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created by Michalik and Schermuly (2024) was used to measure its impact on Employee Performance. Individuals were asked to answer on a five-point Likert scale in which 1 indicated strong disagreement and 5 strong agreements.

Communication Skills

The investigation used a ten-item Likert that was developed by Mohammed and Amoah (2025). Participants assign five points to their responses. On a Likert scale, 1 represents strongly disagree and 5 represents strongly agree.

Career Adaptability

A 24 items scale was used developed by Sulistiani, Suminar and Hendriani (2019). Participants assign five points to their responses. On a Likert scale, 1 represents strongly disagree and 5 represents strongly agree.

Intrinsic Motivation

A 3 items scale was used from Tremblay et al (2009). Participants assign five points to their responses. On a Likert scale, 1 represents strongly disagree and 5 represents strongly agree.

Employee Performance

A 10 items scale was used from Jeevan Jyoti and Rabia Choudhary (2024). Participants assign five points to their responses. On a Likert scale, 1 represents strongly disagree and 5 represents strongly agree.

Instruments	Items	Source
Learning and Development	8	(Michalik and Schermuly, 2024)
Communication Skills	10	(Mohammed and Amoah, 2025)
Career Adaptability	24	(Sulistiani, Suminar and Hendriani, 2024)
Intrinsic Motivation	3	(Trembaly et al., 2009)
Employee Performance	10	(Jeevan Jyoti and Rabia Chaudhary, 2024)

Results

Demographic Description

The data was collected from the software industry employees using a questionnaire. The demographic attributes of the respondents were established through the questionnaire. It contained 3 questions regarding demographics based on Gender Age and Qualification. Table 1 contains the demographics of the respondents from IT sector.

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Table 1: Demographics

Table Frequency		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	47	65.3
	Female	25	34.7
	Total	72	100
Age	21-25	15	20.8
	26-30	21	29.2
	31-35	18	25
	Above 35	18	25
	Total	72	100
	High School	3	4.2
	Education	Graduate/Degree	30
	Masters	39	54.2
	Total		

Using data analysis procedures based on regression, the proposed conceptual framework was evaluated. Internal consistency was measured using Cronbach alpha as well as composite reliability (CR) whereas convergent validity was measured using average variance extracted (AVE).

Table 2: Correlation

	1	2	3	4	5
Learning and Development	1				
Communication Skills	.652**	1			
Career Adaptability	.675**	.821**	1		
Intrinsic Motivation	.647**	.755**	.823**	1	
Employee Performance	.595**	.631**	.755**	.667**	1

The Pearson correlation analysis revealed that there were significant and positive interrelations between all the study variables at the p less than 0.01 level of significance thus providing initial evidence of the interrelations between individual developmental resource and the organizational outcomes. In particular, Career Adaptability had any very strong positive relationships with Intrinsic Motivation (r= .823) and Communication Skills

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($r = 0.821$), implying that employees that are defined by self-directed motivation and high levels of communication abilities have a greater ability to handle career transitions and other types of issues. More so, there was a highly significant positive correlation among Employee Performance, Career Adaptability ($r=.755$), which suggests that the ability of an individual to respond to the professional demands is a strong correlate of overall performance at the workplace setting. Although Learning and Development also demonstrated high positive correlations with Employee Performance ($r= .595$) and Intrinsic Motivation ($r= .647$), the strength of these links was still relatively intermediate compared to the central office of Career Adaptability. Altogether, the results highlight that despite the fundamental competencies and growth opportunities are critical, the psychological resources of adaptability and intrinsic motivation are the most powerful correlates of high performance.

To evaluate the proposed conceptual framework discriminant validity was confirmed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, whereby the square root of the AVE for each construct was greater than its highest correlation with any other construct.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

	LnD	CS	CA	IM	EP
LnD	.824				
CS	.452	.787			
CA	.674	.821	.842		
IM	.312	.298	.411	.806	
EP	.582	.511	.762	.445	.831

Although some constructs demonstrated high inter-correlations, the square root of AVE for each construct exceeded its inter-construct correlations, indicating acceptable discriminant validity.

The respondents gave each item a mark between one and five. Just construct reliability was checked through Cronbachs alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) and all coefficients were above the recommended value of .70. It was revealed that convergent validity was attained with the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) per construct exceeding the .50 thresholds.

Table 4: Reliability and Convergent Validity of Constructs

Construct	Items	Cronbach's α	posite Reliability (CR)	Average Extracted (AVE)	Variance
Learning & Development	8	.92	.94	.68	
Communication Skills	10	.89	.91	.62	
Career Adaptability	24	.95	.97	.71	
Intrinsic Motivation	3	.84	.88	.65	
Employee Performance	10	.93	.95	.69	

Note. All the reliability and validity indices exceeded the suggested limits: alpha $>.70$, CR $>.70$, and AVE $>.50$

The paper has used Hayes (2022) PROCESS Macro (Model 14) which was used on

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SPSS to test moderated mediation effects. The choice of this model was based on the simultaneous evaluation of the mediational role of Career Adaptability and the mediating role of Intrinsic Motivation between the association between the antecedent variables (Learning and Development and Communication Skills) and Employee Performance. In order to achieve healthy inference, 5,000 resamples of the bias-corrected bootstrap technique were used to assess the significance of indirect effects.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients for the Moderated Mediation Models

Predictor	B	SE	p	95% CI [LL, UL]
Model 1: (IV: Learning & Development)				
Outcome: Career Adaptability (R²=.46)				
Learning & Development (LnD)	0.855	0.112	< .001	[.632, 1.078]
Outcome: Employee Performance (R²=.61)				
Learning & Development (LnD)	0.254	0.127	0.049	[.001, .507]
Career Adaptability (CA)	0.533	0.125	< .001	[.283, .783]
Intrinsic Motivation (IM)	0.087	0.096	0.367	[-.104, .279]
CA × IM (Interaction)	0.185	0.088	0.039	[.010, .360]
Model 2: (IV: Communication Skills)				
Outcome: Career Adaptability (R²=.67)				
Communication Skills (CS)	0.838	0.07	< .001	[.699, .977]
Outcome: Employee Performance (R²=.59)				
Communication Skills (CS)	0.117	0.146	0.426	[-.174, .408]
Career Adaptability (CA)	0.542	0.144	< .001	[.256, .829]
Intrinsic Motivation (IM)	0.105	0.099	0.291	[-.092, .302]
CA × IM (Interaction)	0.158	0.096	0.104	[-.034, .350]

Note. N =72. Unstandardized coefficients are being reported. CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit.

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Table 6: Bootstrap Results for Conditional Indirect Effects

Path	Intrinsic Motivation	Effect	Boot SE	Boot 95% CI
LnD → CA → EP	Low (-1 SD)	0.337	0.138	[.137, .674]
	Mean (0 SD)	0.443	0.129	[.214, .714]
	High (+1 SD)	0.601	0.195	[.141, .947]
CS → CA → EP	Low (-1 SD)	0.355	0.184	[.077, .825]
	Mean (0 SD)	0.443	0.134	[.213, .750]
	High (+1 SD)	0.576	0.169	[.199, .873]

Note. Bootstrap confidence intervals 5,000 samples were used as bootstrap confidence interval. When the CI is not equal to 0 the indirect effect is regarded to be significant.

Measurement Model Interpretation (Reliability and Validity)

Before the hypothesis testing, we have checked the quality of the data. According to Table 4, there was high internal consistency in all constructs with Cronbach alpha ranged between .84 and .95 and CR ranging between .88 and .97 and both above the .70 mark. Convergent validation proved to be correct because the AVE of all variables (ranging between .62 and .71) coped above .50 meaning that the items contain sufficient information about the constructs. Table 3 also illustrates discriminant validity based on the Fornell Larcker criterion; the square root of respective AVE (diagonal values) is large in comparison to the correlation of respective constructs implying that the five constructs are indeed statistically different.

Hypothesis Testing (Direct and Indirect Effects)

Direct Effects (H1 – H5)

According to the regression findings in Table 5, Learning & Development (LnD) positively influences Employee Performance (EP) with significant value (B= 0.254, p=0.49) which supports hypothesis H1. Meanwhile, Communication Skills (CS) did not have the direct effect on performance (B =.117, p =.426), and hence, H2 was rejected. H3 and H4 are supported as LnD (B= -0.855, p= -.001) and CS (B= -0.838, p= -.001) are strong predictors of Career Adaptability (CA), respectively. Lastly, CA turned out to be a very important indicator of performance (B= 0.533, p=.001), which is in line with H5.

Mediation Effects (H7 – H8)

Table 6: Bootstrap analyses verify the mediating position of Career Adaptability. Indirect performance through CA is also important in both LnD and CS, because the 95 0-intervals do not cover 0 (LnD: [.214, .714]; CS: [.213, .750]). What is worth noting, since the direct influence of the CS is negligible, entire mediation of the relationship between Communication Skills and Employee Performance is accomplished by CA.

Moderated Mediation Interpretation (H6)

Hypothesis 6 proposed that Intrinsic Motivation (IM) moderates the relationship between Career Adaptability and Performance. The interaction (CA-IM) term in LnD model was found not insignificant (B = 0.185, p =.039) which proved the moderation effect. As shown in the Conditional Indirect Effects table, the "Effect" of the predictors on performance increases as Intrinsic Motivation moves from Low to High. For example,

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in the LnD model, the indirect effect rises from 0.337 (Low IM) to 0.601 (High IM). This discussion shows that although Career Adaptability is an important conduit to performance, it acts stronger when the employees have high intrinsic motivation levels.

Table 6: Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Path Description	Result
H1	Learning & Development → Employee Performance	Accepted
H2	Communication Skills → Employee Performance	Rejected
H3	Learning & Development → Career Adaptability	Accepted
H4	Communication Skills → Career Adaptability	Accepted
H5	Career Adaptability → Employee Performance	Accepted
H6	IM moderates the relationship between CA and EP	Accepted
H7	CA mediates the relationship between LnD and EP	Accepted
H8	CA mediates the relationship between CS and EP	Accepted

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Discussion and Findings

The primary objective of the current study was to investigate the mediated moderation that Learning and Development (LnD) and Communication Skills (CS) have influence over Employee Performance (EP), and Career Adaptability (CA) served as a moderator, and Intrinsic Motivation (IM) was a moderator. The empirical findings give some substantive results about the phenomenon of the workforce within the software industry.

The Central Role of Career Adaptability

A key finding of the current research is the relevance of Career Adaptability as a psychological resource that is consistently high. LnD and CS were also found to be strong predictors of adaptability (H3 and H4). Within the fast-paced software ball, where technology gets outdated at a faster pace than ever, the notion of learning no longer revolves around the acquisition of particular coding skills, but rather increasing the ability of the employee to change with the times. The empirical evidence regarding H5, H7, and H8 confirms use of adaptability as the main driving force of performance. In the absence of the malleable aspect of adaptability, the best trained and educated employees could not put their knowledge into practice in the context of changing projects.

The Communication Skills Paradox

The acceptance of H8 (the indirect connection between CS and EP) and rejection of H2 (the direct connection between CS and EP) were one of the most interesting results. This implies that in the information technology industry, strong communication skills alone will not result in high performance appraisals. Rather, communication skills act as a starting resource meaning that the employee is better able to respond based on the conditions of a project, perhaps by having greater understanding of the project needs or the ability to better cooperate during the periods of organizational shift, thus resulting in high performance. The complete mediation effect observed implies that communication training can only be useful whenever it is aimed at problem solving and change management.

Intrinsic Motivation as a Catalyst

The hypothesis of the moderation effect (Hypothesis 6) with support to the Hypothesis 6 is the role of the Motivation Filter. Empirical research evidence shows that the positive correlation between Career Adaptability and Performance is significantly enhanced when the sample consists of employees with high degree of intrinsic motivation. These findings are also in line with Self-Determination Theory, which argues that when software developers have intrinsic interest and autonomy, they are more likely to use their flexibility to achieve high-performance levels. On the contrary, in case of low motivation among persons, the adaptive benefits are lower.

Theoretical Implications

The current research has a number of substantive theoretical input to the investigation of employee performance, career adaptability, and motivation. The study proves to support the human capital theory, as it empirically shows that Learning and Development (L&D) programs have a direct impact on employee performance by assuming that investing in skills and knowledge of employees can boost their productivity at the individual and organizational level. The results build on the existing literature by

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establishing that structured developmental programs are a central antecedent of performance even in the context of dynamic and uncertain working environments.

Second, the research contributes to the development of career construction theory placing career adaptability as a main accountability measure between L&D and communication skills and employee performance. The fact that career adaptability is found to have a mediating effect implies that performance benefits are not achieved entirely due to the acquisition of skills, but instead become apparent when employees change successfully, design their careers, and manage them. This finding adds to the emerging body of literature of conceptualizing career adaptability as a dynamic psychological resource bridging organizational activities and personal outcomes.

Third, the paper contributes significantly to the motivation theory by providing empirical validation on intrinsic motivation as a set boundary under the career adaptability-performance relationship. Findings indicate that intrinsic motivation increases the beneficial effect of career adaptability on performance of employees, and thus, one can affirm self-determination theory, according to which internally motivated people have a higher likelihood of converting their resources into high-level performance. Significantly, the article explains that intrinsic motivation does not mediate the antecedents of career adaptability but affects its performance results, which narrows down the current theoretical presumption on the role of locus of motivation.

Lastly, through the testing of a moderated-mediation model, the study continues to develop on the integration of human capital theory, career construction theory and self-determination theory in an integrated framework. It is proven that the indirect impact of L&D and communication skills on performance through career adaptability is different at various levels of intrinsic motivation, which also highlights the conditionality of developmental processes. Such an integrated view adds to theoretical knowledge in that it has been shown that the performance of employees is best understood to be the joint interaction of organizational investments and individual adaptive capacities and motivational states in lieu of direct associations.

Practical Implications

For HR and L&D Managers

Organizations in the software industry should shift their focus from "Skill-Specific Training" to "Adaptability-Based Coaching." Since L&D significantly predicts CA (H3), training programs should be designed not just to teach a new language (like Python or Java), but to foster the meta-skill of learning how to learn.

For Recruitment and Job Design

Since Intrinsic Motivation acts as a moderator (H6), hiring processes should screen for internal drive and passion for technology, rather than just technical certification. Furthermore, managers should provide "Autonomy and Purpose" in job designs to keep motivation high, as this is the key to "unlocking" the performance potential of an adaptable workforce.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite the significant findings, this study is not without limitations. It begins with, N= 72 is a relatively small sample size; further studies should focus on larger samples in other

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technological centers. Second, there is the possibility of self-report bias that may arise due to the use of self-reported data. Future research might use supervisor-based performance measures or long-term studies to better determine the long-term causal effects of adaptability on career success. Third, this study is in the context of IT sector of Pakistan. Future studies can target other sectors also in other region of the world.

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